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ASSESSING THE ADMINISTRATION OF GENERAL ELECTIONS IN NIGERIA, 1999-2007

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Abstract: *This paper assessed the conduct of elections in Nigeria against the backdrop of prevailing trends characteristic of the country's electoral process since the return to civil rule in 1999. The article focused on the fourth republic between 1999-2007. The study depended on secondary sources of data and adopted elitist theory of democracy as a framework for analysis. The paper found among other things that, although the 1999-2007 elections succeeded in ensuring transition from civilian to civilian rule, they also generated and transmitted virulent political mishaps that have made democratic elections in the country more treacherous. Accordingly, the paper recommends among other things that the Independent Electoral Commission (INEC) should be restructured with legal framework to enable it control campaigns and party primaries and recommend punishment for contraveners of electoral rules to discourage injurious electoral practices and fiat exclusion of candidates through charade primaries.*

Introduction

In democratic systems, the nexus between elections and political practice generally cannot be overstated. This is because, apart from providing the most civilized means by which the recruitment of those to exercise authority, elections also afford individuals the opportunity for political actions such as voting and other such social interactions. Specifically, elections are

expected to enthrone democratic virtues such as political socialization, participation, representation, responsibility, probity and accountability (Hague & Harrop, 2006; Agbaje, 2006; Heywood, 2007; George-Genyi, 2015). In fact, as Key (1955) sums it up, the success of any democracy depends on the extent to which individuals are allowed to express choice of leadership through popular elections.

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Apparently, electoral politics is an integral part of a functioning democracy providing and saucing a common platform for both politicians and the electorate to come together for mutual bargain, understanding and □authoritative decision□ on affairs of the state (Appadorai, 1975). To this end, there are generally accepted principles or codes of conduct for participants and political parties such as legality, impartiality, transparency, building of coalitions and promotion of civic education among others. While this may hold to be true in some democratic settings, in others such as Nigeria, the conduct of elections is strewn with trajectories that only showcase a travesty of self-seeking democratic process. It may therefore be safe to say that elections in Nigeria since the return to civil rule in 1999 have defied the known ethos and procedures characteristic of a civil process. Hence elections seem to only come *en passant* to legitimize the rule of a ruling □clique’ which has been recycling itself in power while the rest of the citizens have become political spectators who are contacted and manipulated only after every four years.

It was therefore expected that after many years of military intrusions, the first three general elections (1999-2007) would lay a fortified foundation for the future of democracy in Nigeria, for it was assumed that what was left of the old foundation before the military era, was completely vitiated by the vagaries of military

interventions. The Carter Centre in its report (1999) also expressed the hope that the current transition program represents the culmination of a long and difficult process of political transition in Nigeria. According to the Report, the period also represented the first step toward establishing sustainable democracy in a country that is yet to hold two successive presidential elections.

However, all hopes were dashed with the spate of virulent trends that characterized the elections. The politics characterizing these elections coexisted with copious democratic travesties ranging from violence, disenfranchisement, rigging, abuse of human rights, unlawful inclusion and exclusion of candidates by political parties, assassination of political opponents, snatching of ballot boxes, lack of security of voters, and mutilation and falsification of election results, often leading to post-election disharmony, petitions and counter-petitions (INEC & FES, 2011; Ogundiya, 2015). While these foundational elections tended to be inharmonious with the popular ethos of democratic elections, there was an attempt in between to degrade the system to a one-man-show in the name of third term agenda.

The paper therefore, assesses the conduct of elections in Nigeria against the backdrop of trends and trajectories which have become characteristic of the country’ s electoral process since the return to civil rule in 1999. It focuses on

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1999-2007 general elections. Within the period, special attention is placed on National Assembly and Presidential elections which present more common variables.

Conceptual Framework: Elections and electoral politics

Elections can be viewed as a political activity organized by a constituted body of trustworthy and integrity citizens, in democratic society, with independent authority to regulate within the constitutional powers, the process through which voters (electorates) make their choice of those who will represent them in governance. He further maintained that in liberal democracy, it is a viable mechanism for consummating representative government. Apart from facilitating succession, it also promotes accountability, citizens' participation and give voice and power to the people. In similar terms, Ogundiya (2015) opined that elections are a sine qua non for a functional democracy, and procedurally, democracy is inconceivable without elections because, elections provide the tools for the electorate or citizens to determine who governs them and perhaps how. The above views of elections contain most of the basic functions of democratic elections like choosing and controlling political leaders.

Having aggregated scholarly opinions about the subject matter, paper adopts Janda, Berry and Goldman' s (2005, p.271) view that elections are □organized□ platforms for reaching

□authoritative decision□ on who controls the institutions of the state, particularly the legislature and the executive, and to also control the end they pursue. For elections to serve this indispensable purpose, the electorate must have real alternatives for them to exercise their choice and the choice of the majority must always be allowed to prevail.

Methodology

Data for this study was gathered using secondary sources. The secondary data was then subjected to analysis which led to the key findings and conclusions relating to the general elections of 1999, 2003 and 2007. The chief justification for deploying secondary sources of data stem from the mass availability and tracking of the elections proceedings by credible databases; data which general people would hadly recall.

Theoretical framework

The roots of elitist theory are traced to sociology particularly to two Italian sociologists; Vilfredo Pareto and Gaetano Mosca and the German sociologist, Robert Michels who first saw the utopianism of mass rule owing to the inevitability of elite rule. Other proponents of the theory include C.W. Mills, Harold Lasswell, and Hywel Williams. They saw certain common characteristics among the elite such as unity, dominance and the ability to replace themselves (Haralambos & Holborn, 2008; Gauba, 2007; Janda, Berry & Goldman, 2005). Michels became famous with his □iron law of oligarchy' which

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suggests that the elite exist in every sphere of human association including the so-called democracy. In his view, democracy is in the actual sense the rule of the elite. Hence elections are a platform for competition between two or more elite groups for the power to govern the state where only a low level of citizen participation is required. The elitist notion of elections discard the normative values and expressions such as 'voice of the people' or 'rule of the general will', it instead promotes the rule by the chosen few (Johari, 2009).

According to Gauba (2007), the elitist theory has added an empirical dimension to democratic theory. This is because it has pointed out clearly the prime reason for electoral struggle which have not excluded democratic systems. It has also pointed out clearly why majority of citizens of a given society may become disillusioned with politics because they have been side-lined, or are not fit to compete with the 'mighty' elites. In other words, this paper is anchored on the elitist theory of democracy which is the belief in the social superiority of some people. Central to the theory is that there is always a small group of people making most of the important government decisions. The theory rejects the proposition by popular democratic theorists that democracy is the rule of the people, and it ridicules such concepts as 'general will' and 'popular participation'. It believes that society is divided into two main groups: a ruling

minority who exercises state power, and the majority (powerless) who constitutes the ruled. The ruling minority has monopolized power in the society to the exclusion of the rest of the majority groups.

The elitist theory has been accused of using a crafty notion of democracy, power politics and election to stripe them of any element of normativism. It is also accused of promoting a view about democracy that attempts to side-line the masses from government by conceding minimal role to them in voting to choose the ruling elites. Again, it has reduced democratic practices such as elections and voting to mere activity to select the few individuals to lord over the people.

A point of observation has to be made however, that the accusations against the elitist theorists appear to be misdirected since they only observed and explained what is in practice. Therefore, the theory fits here so long as it can observe and explain the spate of electoral travelogue in Nigeria.

Facts and Figures about the 1999 General Elections

The 1999 general elections were held on February 20 (the National and State Assemblies) and on 27 February 1999 (for the Gubernatorial and the Presidential). These were the first elections since the 1993 military coup and the first in the Fourth Nigerian Republic. The total number of registered voters stood at 57,938,954;

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total vote cast (turnout for presidential), 30,280,052 (52.3%); invalid votes, 431, 611; and total valid votes were 29,848,441. For the Senate the number of registered voters was 57,938,954; total votes cast were 24,386,247 (42.1%), while that of the House of Representatives was 57,938,954 with a total vote cast of 23,573,407 (40.7%) respectively (<http://africanelections.tripod.com/ng.html>).

The presidential elections were contested by two major political parties; the People's Democratic Party (PDP) and the Alliance for Democracy-All People's Party (AD-APP). The result was a landslide victory for Olusegun Obasanjo of the PDP who pooled a total of 18,738,154 votes (62.78%), while Olu Falae, who run on a joint ticket of AD-APP got 11,110,287 (37.22%). For the National Assembly, PDP won 59 Senate seats and 206 House of Representatives seats, APP won 29 Senate seats and 74 House of Representatives seats, AD won 20 Senate seats and 68 House of Representative seats, while there were 1 and 12 vacant seats in Senate and House of Representatives respectively (<http://africanelections.tripod.com/ng.html>).

According to the Carter Centre Report (1999), of the 35 gubernatorial seats contested, the PDP won 20, followed by the APP with nine, and the AD with six. The election in Bayelsa State which is located in the troubled Niger Delta region in

the far south, was postponed due to violent clashes over the distribution of the state's oil wealth.

2003 General Elections

The 2003 General elections were held on 12 April 2003 (for the National Assembly) and on 19 April 2003 (for the Presidential elections). A total of 60,823,022 voters registered for both National Assembly and presidential elections. The total vote cast for the Presidential elections was 42,018,735 (69.1%); invalid votes, 2,533,248; and total valid votes, 39,480,489. The total vote cast for the Senate was 29,995,171 (49.3%); invalid votes, 965,064; total valid votes, 29,030,107. The House of Representatives was 30,386,270 representing (50.0%) turnout. Invalid votes amounted to 1,153,200 and vildid votes were 29,233,070 respectively (<http://africanelections.tripod.com/ng.html>).

According to African Elections Tripod (2003), the 2003 Presidential elections were contested by 20 political parties. However, the main political parties were PDP and ANPP. The Presidential election was won overwhelmingly by the then President, Olusegun Obasanjo of the PDP who pooled a total of 24,456,140 (61.94%) votes while Muhammadu Buhari of the ANPP came second with 12, 710, 022 (32.19%). The rest of the figures are presented on Table 1.1

Table 1.1 Result of 2003 Presidential Elections in Nigeria

S/No	Party	Total Votes Received	Percentage of Votes Received (%)
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1.	PDP	24,456,140	61.94
2.	ANPP	12,710,022	32.19
3.	APGA	1,297,445	3.29
4.	Others	860,039	2.58

Source: Author's Computation

The main parties that contested and won the National Assembly elections were PDP (76 Senate seats and 223 House of Representatives seats), ANPP (23 Senate seats and 96 House of Representatives), and AD (6 Senate seats and 34 House of Representatives). Other parties were UNPP, 2; NDP, 1; APGA, 2; and PRP 1, House of Representatives seats respectively. House of representative seat was vacant (<http://africanelections.tripod.com/ng.html>).

2007 General Elections

Both the Presidential and the National Assembly elections of 2007 were held on 21 April, 2007.

Table 2.1 Result of 2007 Presidential Elections in Nigeria

S/No	Party	Total Votes Received	Percentage of Votes Received (%)
1.	PDP	24,638,063	69.60
2.	ANPP	6,605,299	18.66
3.	AC	12,637,848	7.45
4.	Others	1,516,307	4.29

Source: Author's Computation

African Election Tripod database and indeed that of INEC did not host figures on the governorship and House of Representative elections for 2007.

Popular Opinion about the 1999, 2003 and 2007 Elections

For the presidential election, 25 political parties fielded candidates and vied for a total of 61,567,036 registered votes. Out of the 35,397,517 valid votes counted, the candidate of the PDP, Umaru Musa Yar Ádua won the elections with 24,638,063 (69.60%). Muhammadu Buhari of the ANPP came second with total votes of 6,605,299 (18.66%), while Atiku Abubakar of the AC received 2,637,848 (7.45%) to come third. Other political parties that contested and received a total of 1,516,307 (4.29). The summary of the votes are presented on table 2.1

Regarding the popular view about the conduct and outcome of the 1999, 2003 and 2007 elections, Omotola (2010, p.188) summed up views from different sources that:

There is widespread belief, backed by intimidating evidence that the quality of Nigerian elections nose-dives with successive

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elections, as was the case with the 1999, 2003 and 2007 general elections. Though long standing, the deepening crisis of electoral governance in Nigeria has recently assumed epidemic proportions, creating an urgent need for electoral reform. Over the years, Nigerian elections have offered the electorate little or no genuine choices, leading a consistent student of Nigerian politics to conclude that the history of elections in the country is one of 'electoral fraud and competitive rigging' .

(This trend, as evidenced most recently in the 2007 general elections, has degenerated into a situation where results are concocted for areas where no voting actually took place. For instance, in 2007 there were reported cases of elections not being held or many registered voters being disenfranchised in several parts of the South-East and South-South. Reasons for this included violence and the non-availability, late arrival, or shortage of voting materials.

Omotola's report corroborated that of The Carter Centre (1999) which indicated that the 1999 General Elections were characterised by abuse of the electoral process that manifested in ballot stuffing, inflation of results, and voter intimidation which discredited the outcome of the elections.

Oni, Erameh & Oladejo (2017) also averred that the 2007 elections recorded copious legal cases to an alarming tone of 6,180. According to them, this may be correct given the high level of

political gangsterism and the political culture of impunity that characterized the party politics prior to elections in Nigeria. Omotola (2010) related the numerous court cases to the manipulation of party primaries to pave the way for 'anointed' candidates of the godfathers. Where this failed, the party hierarchy resorted to elimination by substituting the names of the preferred candidates in place of those who actually won the primaries.

In any electoral process, party mechanisms such as primaries which, ordinarily, are internal affairs of the political parties can truly become a nightmare to an entire democratic process. These can be turned into crooked means of excluding popular candidates and denying voters the opportunity to make real political choices with their votes. In Nigeria, for instance, over the years, party primaries have been a major log in the democratization process as EU EOM (2015, p.19) elaborated below:

There is insufficient legal regulation of party primaries, with INEC lacking powers of enforcement. As INEC is legally barred from disqualifying candidates, the candidate nomination procedure is essentially a clerical exercise. Therefore, the party primaries enjoy a wide margin of discretion with challenge only possible through judicial processes' the primaries, which can have between a few hundred and 8,000 delegates and can last over

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24 hours, may be characterized as having the form of an election with safeguards.

Observing the trend in the general elections of 1999, 2003, and 2007, Omotola (2010, p. 189) insisted thus;

Party primaries were mere rituals, allowing no room for internal party democracy. Candidates were largely imposed by “godfathers” and, when their scheming failed, leading to the emergence of an “un-anointed” candidate, the godfathers resorted to substitution by elimination, using the INEC, the agency which has the overall responsibility for electoral administration in Nigeria. But the fact that it is constituted by the President, coupled with the absence of an independent source of funding and its reliance largely on the Presidency for its finances means its independence is severely compromised, making it vulnerable to executive manipulation through the power of incumbency. Another strong event that might have affected the politics of the 2007 elections was the third term agenda that came up ahead of the General Elections in 2007. The 2007 elections were to witness for the first time in the history of independent Nigeria the transition of power from civilian to civilian government, as the two terms constitutionally allowed for the incumbent president was going to terminate at that time.

There were copious opinions that the then President, Olusegun Obasanjo moved to influence the National Assembly to change the

constitutional clause which limits the executive to only two terms, to allow him seek for a third term in office. One of such opinions was expressed by a member of the administration, Nasir El Rufai. El Rufai (2013, p.355) was quoted to have said the following:

With the third term distraction out of the way, attention could only then turn to who would succeed Obasanjo. There are those who say Obasanjo’s revenge for his third term defeat was intentionally picking two incompetent people to be president and vice-president...he thought they were weak people he could control and through whom he could continue to exercise power. I think that he thought Yar’Ádua would be an acceptable president, but would be weak and subservient to him in many policy areas and would be consulting him regularly so that Obasanjo might be a Lee Kuan Yew sort of figure, exercising power from behind the scene.

The events before the 2007 elections heated the polity but led to the eventual emergence of new political leaders that controlled post 2007 elections. Whether it was the 1999, 2003 or 2007 elections, common trends characterised them.

Common trends that characterized elections and electoral politics of 1999, 2003 and 2007

i. The elections were won and lost by two major political parties, the first instance being PDP vs AD-APP, the second and third instance being PDP and ANPP;

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ii. PDP dominated the elections by winning the presidential and majority slots in all the regions (both the senate and the house of representatives);

iii. The elections were a test of the ability of the nation, particularly INEC to truly ensure the consolidation of democracy;

iv. The elections ensured civilian to civilian transition for the first time in the history of independent Nigeria;

v. The three elections were characterized by fraud, violence, intimidation, and undermining of electoral rules meant to ensuring free, fair and credible process;

vi. The elections reasserted the influence of money in Nigerian politics;

vii. The elections showed lack of education and the presence of political apathy among the electorates, as they all witnessed low turnout and massive invalid votes;

viii. The electoral politics, particularly the conduct of primaries in all the elections was a façade of a democratic process; and

ix. All the elections pointed that the electorates are not in control of government in Nigeria as it is claimed by democracy.

Conclusion

After many years of military rule and its vagaries, the 1999-2007 elections were expected to enthroned and nurture a virile democracy in Nigeria. Though the elections succeeded in ensuring transition from military to civilian rule

for the first time since the history of independent Nigeria, they were marred with several irregularities. What was more obvious was that the elections either returned to the era of fraudulent and violent electoral politics, or unveiled new trends that were hitherto obscured in Nigerian elections and electoral politics. For instance, the issue of godfatherism became so pronounced in the elections and more citizens were excluded from the political processes and there were no indications that the system cared about the electorates.

In fact, left for the electorate alone, Obasanjo could have succeeded with his tenure elongation project through his new tactics of □Ghana-must-go-politics□. He failed only because his elitist clique disagreed with him and overly united to defeat him to pave way for another one of them to occupy the top seat. It will be safe to say the the elections succeeded in generating, promoting and transiting virulent political means, such as violence, outright abuse of electoral rules, imposition of candidates, intimidation among others that have made democratic elections in the country even more treacherous today.

Recommendations

i. For democracy to take roots and become institutionalized, there is need to open more space for fair and transparent citizens' participation without molestation and bias.

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ii. Nigerian political parties should de-emphasise politics along the lines of religion, tribe, regions and character assassination that tend to divide the country, but focus on issue-based politics.

iii. INEC should be restructured with legal framework to enable it control campaigns and party primaries and punish contraveners of electoral rules. This will discourage injurious electoral practices and arbitrary exclusion of candidates through charade primaries.

iv. The Federal government should ensure the provision of more security to guarantee the safety of voters and their votes during elections. Measures should be put in place to ensure that such security personnel are not manipulated by politicians.

v. The choices of the general masses should always be allowed to count if elections are to truly

serve their conventional role of bringing citizens together for agreement on important decisions of the state like who rules, what policies to pursue and how to pursue them. All stakeholders in national development owe the people this sacred duty.

vi. For elections to be truly the test of democracy there is need to allow them to be competitive so as to give the electorate a wide range of opportunities and choices. This is the responsibility of politicians and the electoral management body, INEC.

vii. Finally, Government agencies in collaboration with the INEC and civil society organisations should intensify voter education to minimize high level of invalid ballots recorded during the three elections under review and to boost the confidence of electorates to vote in future elections.

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